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POSTCOLONIAL READING/REREADING AS DECOLONISING EMANCIPATORY PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an attempt is made to study the postcolonial ventures on biblical studies as a critique of the existing knowledge discourses of Bible which the colonizers introduced to the colonized. This attempt is necessitated due to the understanding by the scholars from the Third World that Bible is/was used as a tool to serve the interests of colonial powers, both European as well as the native colonising powers. In this article, the European colonial powers are identified as the forces which served to stabilise the powers in the colonised geography through economical and cultural means; the native colonial powers are understood as the forces from within which colonised the minds of the native through the hegemonic discourses of caste, gender, language, religion, etc. Postcolonial criticism is a style of enquiry as it provides a platform for the widest possible convergence of critical forces, of multi-ethnic, multi-religious and multi-cultural, in order to assert the denied rights of the colonized. In this context, postcolonial project of decolonisation gets a radical humanist face; decolonisation itself is understood as a platform for the transformative politics against any sort of discrimination, carried out in the name of gender, caste, race, religion, colour, etc. Postcolonial criticism, in this sense, offers the convergence of many such localised issues, but universally addressed as a venture against discriminatory practices involving knowledge, power and practices. A re-writing often implicates the reader as an active agent in determining the meanings made possible by the dialogue between the source-text and its re-writing, according to the postcolonial reading/rereading strategies.

Key Words: Postcolonialism, Reading, Criticism, Biblical studies, Decolonisation

INTRODUCTION

Postcolonialism is a discipline where everything is contested from the standpoint of the oppressed and the colonized. Having begun in 1960s after the demise of formal European